

Mathematical Continuity and Buddhist Views of Self

Douglas Geiger

June 2025

1 Abstract

In this paper, I will be exploring a potential analogy between mathematical continuity of functions and Buddhist views of self. This will take place assuming a background metaphysics of analytic idealism (which is the view that unified consciousness is the only "real" thing in reality and everything else is derived from it). Let me clarify a few points. The point of this paper is to see if an analogy between continuity of functions on the real number line is useful in making sense of Buddhist views of the self. This is not a paper intended to prove any metaphysical claims. It is also not a highly technical and mathematically rigorous paper. Instead, it should be seen as a written thought experiment.

2 Introduction

There are many different schools of Buddhism with many similar but somewhat divergent views of self. I will choose a view that I think is very compatible with analytical idealism. This approach will be an attempt to make sense of the question "what gives us the illusion of a permanent self?" We will think about how an answer based on continuity of functions might provide us with an answer. To start, we will assume that the self is not permanent, but a stream of mentally continuous phenomena. The broader mental space through which this stream flows will be universal consciousness, or universal mind at large. Given this picture, we will attempt to draw analogies with real analysis to think how we might model the perception we have that are self-is permanent.

3 Background: Momentariness in Buddhism

In interpreting Abhidhamma pitika, there seem to be two views of the flow of self. One view is that the self flows in discrete moments so quickly that it may seem continuous and permanent. Another view is that the self flows continuously, and this itself gives rise to the illusion of permanence. We will

assume the latter.

If we assume this latter view, namely, that the self flows continuously, how exactly might we think of what gives rise to this illusion of self?

4 Light Review of Continuity

Using *Introduction to Real Analysis* by Wade, we will make the following definition:

Definition 4.1. *Let $a \in \mathbb{R}$, let I be an open interval which contains a , and let f be a real function defined everywhere on I except possibly at a . Then $f(x)$ is said to converge to L , as x approaches a , if and only if for every $\varepsilon > 0$ there is a $\delta > 0$ (which in general depends on ε, f, I , and a) such that*

$$0 < |x - a| < \delta$$

implies

$$|f(x) - L| < \varepsilon. \tag{1}$$

In this case we write

$$L = \lim_{x \rightarrow a} f(x) \quad \text{or} \quad f(x) \rightarrow L \quad \text{as} \quad x \rightarrow a,$$

and call L the limit of $f(x)$ as x approaches a .

For example, if $f(x) = x$ then as x approaches 3, f approaches 3 since we can choose $\delta = \varepsilon$ and we satisfy the definition of a limit.

We can now define continuity

Definition 4.2. *1. f is said to be continuous at a point $a \in E$ if and only if given $\varepsilon > 0$ there exists a $\delta > 0$ (which in general depends on ε, f , and a) such that*

$$|x - a| < \delta \quad \text{and} \quad x \in E$$

implies

$$|f(x) - f(a)| < \varepsilon.$$

2. f is said to be continuous on E (notation: $f : E \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is continuous) if and only if f is continuous at every $x \in E$.

As for our last example of $f(x) = x$, since $f(3) = 3$, f is continuous at 3. Similarly, f is continuous at every real number.

We can now think about the illusion of self. Let $M(t)$ be a "mental function of time." So at time t the mind (for an individual) is at $M(t)$. Let us suppose that M is continuous and even smooth (no sharp points in its graph on the x-y plane). Then for every δ that is positive, we have a neighborhood of points

$x \in \{ t : |t| \leq \delta \}$. Furthermore, if M is continuous at time t there is a neighborhood of points in the delta neighborhood that implies "closeness" in the epsilon neighborhood of mental events. This may be thought of as being perceived as permanent because these mental events are extremely close to each other and smooth enough that the mental states do not seem to be changing that much at all. So, for close enough time periods, mental events seem to be close enough where no real change is noticed at all, hence creating a sense of self.

5 Modeling the Self as a Continuous Function

We saw in the previous section that we might think of mental phenomena as a function $M(t)$ that is smooth and continuous and changes are not as noticeable the closer in time we are (using the ϵ, δ notion of continuity)

Suppose we wanted to go a little deeper and insist that "identity" is not bound up with all mental phenomena, but only certain ones. This can be accommodated as well. Think of a smooth and continuous function $I(x)$ which is a identity function, the function of what seems to be persistent identity across time (in the single variable case, which we focus on in this paper, I might be a function of a single variable x , for example, x being "awareness" but this could be extended to more variables one thinks should go into the identity function, but this will also expand the notion of continuity into multi-variable functions). Then, we can maybe let $M(t)$ not be so smooth at every point (for example, sharp points may indicate one loosing one's temper) and instead let the identity function be required to be smooth and continuous (or at least smooth enough, perhaps smooth almost everywhere but the few not smooth points might be points where for one reason or other one does not feel like oneself.)

6 Critique and Reflection

Thinking of the mind as a function may be problematic for more than the few reasons I will list here. Firstly, we obviously modeled the function in one variable whereas in reality it is probably more complex. Furthermore, I do not see a straight forward way of modeling the Buddhist idea of rebirth using this continuous function model. Lastly, we did not come up with an explicit formula for the mental function, we merely treated it in the abstract.

7 Conclusion

We attempted to think of the illusion of self in Buddhist metaphysics as a continuous and smooth mental and/or identity function. We hypothesized that the closeness in time and the closeness in function values might give rise to the perception that the self has not really changed.

Further directions of this paper to explore might be differentiability of functions

and karma (how karma influences the rate of change of mental phenomena and direction of the flow) and how this model we explored of the mind might be interpreted under the Buddhist view of no-self.

8 References

- Wade, W. R. (2004). *An introduction to analysis* (3rd ed.). Pearson Education.
- Thompson, E. (2015). *Waking, dreaming, being: Self and consciousness in neuroscience, meditation, and philosophy*. Columbia University Press.
- Kastrup, B. (2023). *Analytic idealism in a nutshell: A brief overview of the theory and its implications*. Iff Books.
- Bhikkhu Bodhi. (2000). *A comprehensive manual of Abhidhamma: The Abhidhammattha Sangaha of Ācariya Anuruddha* (Buddhist Publication Society, Ed.). Pariyatti Publishing.